

**CHILDREN'S LITERATURE (FALKIOR) HIS STUDENTS WITH
THE HELP OF HIS WORKS EDUCATION IN THE SPIRIT OF
NATIONAL VALUES**

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Annotation . This article provides information about folkloric works in primary classes and methods of educating them in the spirit of national values through folklore works.

Keywords. Falklore , elementary class in the textbook tools , national ability , education , methods .

Until now, literary education has been studied as part of the mother tongue teaching methodology. As the methodology of teaching literature in secondary general education has its own status as an independent science, it is an attempt to scientifically and methodologically justify the fact that Methodist scholars should consider the methodology of literary education in primary education as an independent science of methodology. are doing

It is known that in the 2nd half of the 20th century, the idea of studying the artistic work as a work of art with an aesthetic approach to the work of art was put forward in the methodology of the primary school, while psychological research is a different approach to introducing the world of literature to the potential ability of young students. demands.

As each subject has its own learning object and subject, nowadays the idea that the method of reading in primary classes should work as a method of literary education is being promoted. In fact, as a preparatory subject for the systematic course of literature teaching, the methodology of reading defines its goals and tasks based on examples of children's literature. Based on this, it is appropriate to define the learning object of primary school reading classes as the process of students' acquisition of literary education.

The term "literary education" includes three interrelated processes: 1) personal education in the process of contact with literary and artistic works; 2) teaching, i.e. teaching children's literature as one of the school subjects; 3) formation of personal development.

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Aesthetic education of a person in connection with reading works of art, i.e. imparting knowledge, educating and forming beliefs; that is, it is necessary to study examples of children's literature as works of art, like subjects taught at school.

A 1st grade student cannot set such goals (goal: to become spiritually mature, to fill cultural gaps, to master the art of speech. The teacher sets these goals What are you reading? Think about why we are reading this work? Have you mastered this work well with our current method of reading and analysis?

Later, during the lessons, the student learns what he needs to know to become a reader, that a good book creates different experiences (concern, anxiety) in the reader, encourages him to think, and allows him to choose his own position.

In teaching the current literary education, the school encourages the growing young generation to master the culture that was created hundreds of years ago during the history of mankind and has been filled until now. At the same time, schoolchildren

preparing the child for real life, conscious respectively occupation to choose reach demand is putting Of this for of students opportunities and main activities account in case of teaching each one stage school literary education support goals set get it is necessary

That's it we emphasize should be literary education stages present education stages right doesn't come Primary education students of schools around people with cultured treatment to do to teach

Primary the reading lessons of the classes have a special place in the educational system according to their essence, goals and tasks. Because the foundations of literacy and moral-educational education are based on it. Therefore, the education of other subjects cannot be imagined without the education of reading.

For this purpose, the "Reading Book" textbooks include various topics such as mother nature, the world around us, the history and current image of our country, the lives of adults and children, hard work, independence and national-spiritual values, friendship between nations and peace. artistic, moral-educational, scientific-popular works intended to provide comprehensive understanding of

Specific topics included in the "Reading Book" textbooks of the primary class are determined by the fact that they introduce students to the magical world of fiction, and focus on the correct formation of their worldviews based on the ideology of national independence. Accordingly, the leading feature of reading classes is focused on educating students in the spirit of high moral values on the basis of national ideology, while ensuring students' literacy.

The subject range of the works studied in the reading classes of primary grades is quite wide, and they are within general topics such as mother nature, seasons,

folklore, love of work, main holiday dates, national independence and spirituality. combined.

Topics of socio-historical content give a certain idea about the past of our country, the life of our people, heroic struggle, works done by great figures, historical dates. Among them are texts about Beruni, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Babur and other ancestors. These kinds of works not only introduce the students to our past, but also help them to deeply understand their filial duty and responsibility towards the Motherland. This is how the feeling of love for the Motherland is formed in them. In the process of getting acquainted with the works that tell about the past of our country and analyzing them, the students will have the opportunity to compare the past with the present day, they will have a brief understanding of the development of the society.

It is well known to all of us that the priceless cultural masterpieces created by mankind are first of all embodied in **the folklore art** of any nation . The art of Bakhchik, which expresses the national identity of different peoples, their language and way of life, traditions and customs, is valuable for all of us as an integral part of universal culture. [1]

Folklore (English . folk - people , lore - knowledge , wisdom) - people creativity expressive the term English in 1846 archaeologist W. J. Thoms take entered " Folklore " in 1880-1990 . the term is many used in countries , including Russia started in Uzbekistan originally , " oral literature " , " mouth literature " terms used . " Folklore " . term from the mid -30s used started In 1939, Hodi Zarif's " Uzbek folklore " chrestomaty publication after , this the term Uzbek in folklore studies strong place received (cf People creativity , folklore). [2]

Primary class students for education and education in the process first of all there is mother to the motherland has been love - love wake up bite it is necessary for people oral creativity , national our values in itself collected traditions our achievements big place holds " The story Gorogli sultan " , " With Yusuf Ahmad » like that ethnographic and people oral creativity not showing which works young generation spiritual-educational , moral doctrine in giving should be results shows .

Primary in classes oral creativity folk folklore and ethno-cultural education common structural part as small age school in their students national the self awareness , positive national tradition the system of the person spiritual-ethical , social , general cultural and intellectual development for wide to opportunities have That 's it education quality in consideration received without , of our Republic small school students ethno-cultural folklore in the spirit bring up duties , national which improves our values principles work exit necessity born. Ethnic and folklore of doctrine start the content class interdisciplinary integration and of sciences

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innovation ideological applications based on done increase to the goal suitable Class team with didactic games based on done increase and new ideological efficiency level practical and theoretical knowledge present reach of children to his mind effect to transfer big impulse will be Primary class students basically game through faster to science interest in consideration will receive if we this folklore game practical such as fields separate stands of our country start drinking of classes study to the process ethno-cultural the component current reach according to first of all some problems eliminate reach this health increases .

these problems ;

Primary class in their students to his age special in case personal spiritual and moral development again improvement ;

Small school to the students special respectively ethno-cultural education manual programs formation measures ;

Basis as young students for game shape changed without i.e small groups too to groups being connect different filchlor names with evaluation .

Primary class students of course get excited to be this lesson in the process theoretical from knowledge use level reduced without basically practical i.e textbook for special equipment using lesson to give this lesson quality designation with one road his the effect increases . Lesson time children the eye with according to take , take through being able to feel the shape this student in memory sealing and new thoughts and ideas to injury reason will be Textbook tools electronicization and demonstrative weapons with enrichment in momentum developed going present contemporary technology century our youth worthy place occupation , foreign education from the standards not staying software practical the results Create and efficiency to increase service does

Folklore and cultural content modern initial of classes study to the process access the following tasks solution to do expected :

- students own mother of culture come output , people traditions with to introduce

- folklore-cultural reality , own of the people to himself characteristic , national features and family traditions about to practice directed knowledge with enrichment ;

- humane , thoughtful , free the person , own of the people cultural from the inheritance skillful keeper and the user formation ;

- different folklore to groups , their marriage style , work , traditions relatively positive emotional relationship formation ;

- a lot nationality in society international communication to harmonize help giving relationships ;
- a lot cultured in space sorry breadth to the rules , healthy marriage style national to their traditions compliance to do skills formation ;
- **Education** is broad in the sense that or this of adjectives or social of groups goals according to of people new to his descendants first generations socio - historical experience transmission tool with of society development provider task [3]

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